

THE ROLE AND CHARACTERISTICS OF ELECTRIC CARS IN OUR LIFE

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Abstract. An electric car is a car with an electric battery. There are such car models that can be started from solar energy. Electric cars do not need gasoline, there is no gearbox. Google and other giants participate in the development of self-driving cars that work with computer data in production. Billions of dollars are invested in the automotive industry every year. It is used for electric cars in some countries of Asia, Europe and the USA. The infrastructure necessary for this is actively developing: lamps with the ability to charge cars, etc. Electric vehicle production is developing in Russia. for, electric car models of well-known Russian brands are taking a big step into the world markets.

WHAT IS AN ELECTRIC CAR?

An electric car is a car with an electric battery. There are such car models that can be started from solar energy. Electric cars do not need gasoline, there is no gearbox. Google and other giants participate in the development of self-driving cars that work with computer data in production. Billions of dollars are invested in the automotive industry every year. It is used for electric cars in some countries of Asia, Europe and the USA. The infrastructure necessary for this is actively developing: lamps with the ability to charge cars, etc. Electric vehicle production is developing in Russia. for, electric car models of well-known Russian brands are taking a big step into the world markets. China can produce the most powerful electric cars for its export in the whole world. The greenhouse effect threatens the ecological condition of our planet. This phenomenon occurs due to the exhaust gases of the car. Deterioration of the environment and threats to nature are the consequences of burning gasoline, which is the basis of this industry. Do not panic, scientists and experts are developing the cars of the future -

electric cars. In the 70s, at the height of the global energy crisis, interest in alternative energy sources. Research in this area was actively conducted. But when the crisis was over, everyone happily forgot about it. About electric cars again in the nineties and two thousand years, when the gas pollution of the world's largest cities reached its peak (and still). Then the government decided to introduce electric cars to stabilize the environmental situation.

HISTORY OF THE EMERGENCE AND USE OF ELECTRIC CARS.

This car model appeared in the distant XX century. In the era of steam engines, the creation of relatively compact vehicles powered by an electric motor was in the first place. However, the potential of electric cars is not fully revealed due to the shortcomings of this car. The electric car was not designed for long trips and almost always caused difficulties due to the need to charge. electric cars are cheaper than conventional cars it moves almost silently on the roads an expensive, bulky and not always reliable quick transfer box will not be needed 0101does not consume engine oil an electric car can use regenerative braking to recharge its electronic

battery electric power generating shock absorbers can also be used for recharging Expert: To give you an idea of the difference between the prices of gasoline and electric charging: a charge of approximately 25,000 soums will cover a distance of 500 km. 400,000 to 900,000 will be spent to fill the gas tank of other cars. it is said that the electric car can travel 318 km at full power. However, the car covered a distance of 280-300 km with full power. "Electric cars have 20-30 percent less power in winter, and therefore they drive around 220-250 km instead of 318 km," he writes. The blogger clarified that it is not possible to charge at home because he lives in apartment buildings. At the charging point he uses, there is a station that provides 7 kW of electricity per hour - 1 kW/h of power is 450 soums. In addition, there is a service fee of 5000 soums per hour. There is also a parking fee of 3,000 soums per hour if the capacity is full and the car is not towed. It is said that this payment was made to encourage the speedy release of space for other electric cars. "In some places, there are stations that provide 30, 40, 60 kW/h. They can charge the car to 100 percent capacity in less than 1 hour. But such charging is harmful for the battery, - says Umid Gafurov. - It takes 8-10 hours to fully charge at 3.5 kW/h charging stations." When contacted for more information, he said that he still has a positive opinion about electric cars and that after the above post he bought a second and third electric car (replaced with the previous one) and charging shared with these numbers on he wrote that the more properly the battery is used, the more it will last. Almost all manufacturers guarantee batteries for 150,000 km or 8 years. After this period, it works 70-80 percent, not 100 percent. Because over time, the battery degrades,

that is, its resource decreases. For example, he will walk 200 km instead of 300 km. It is natural that everything wears out over time. Older model batteries may only have 1% less capacity to reach full range. It is also reduced by driving with high pressure and driving with high voltage. You can run the latest cars from 0% to 100% with no problem. Using it down to 0 percent is definitely recommended only when charging is near. It is recommended to fill the previous batteries up to 90-95%, and connect them to the station when they reach 10%. Car battery capacity can also increase when the air temperature is average. But it lasts less when the day is cold. The reason is that in the cold, the battery retains its reserve power in order to maintain its size and properties. If we start to compare the internal parts of an electric vehicle with a conventional one, they are not much different. Its operation is very similar. The main elements that make up this electric car are. Electric motor. It is responsible for converting electrical energy stored in batteries into kinetic energy. With this, the car can move. Engines can also do the opposite, that is, on downhill slopes, they use the captured kinetic energy and store it in the form of electricity. Storms.

MOTOR DE COMBUSTIÓN

MOTOR DE ELÉCTRICO

Something that collects electrical energy used to run a motor. There are some vehicles that have an auxiliary battery to keep them grounded. Loading port. What happened to the plug

that connects to the power source that recharges the car battery? Transformers. They are responsible for converting the parameters of electricity into what is needed to charge the

batteries. There are vehicles that run on alternating current and others on direct current. They also serve to cool

the car, prevent spills and explosions. Controllers They regulate the input of energy to the battery. In this way, you can balance the charge appropriately to extend its useful life and not degrade it. Autonomous cars have some advantages over other vehicles. They are as follows Because they are quieter, reduce noise pollution in cities. If all vehicles in the city center were electric, there would be no such noise. Of course, an electric taxi drove past you today and you didn't even hear about it. Noise also affects people's health. Therefore, it is important to reduce it. They do not pollute, which improves air quality in cities. During their use, they do not emit harmful gases that pollute the air in cities and increase the effects of climate change and global warming. Thousands of people die every year from respiratory diseases as a result of air pollution. Zero emission capability. To generate electricity, if we use fossil fuels, we emit gases not in use, but in production. Therefore, electric cars have the ability to be zero emissions. This happens when renewable energies like solar and wind are used to generate electricity. The engine is just as powerful and cheaper. They usually have almost the same power as conventional ones and are more compact and reliable. The problem is the autonomy of the battery. There are no elements that cause the engine to fail. More efficiency and less consumption. The efficiency of electric cars reaches 30% compared to 90% of conventional ones. They consume less and we save more. To perform the same effort, they require less energy, only batteries provide this energy for a short time.

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